

SIMD Acceleration of Matrix-Vector Operations on RISC-V for Variable Precision Neural Networks

Gonzalo Salinas^{†‡}, Guilherme Sequeira^{*}, Alfonso Rodríguez[†], João Bispo^{*} and Nuno Paulino^{*}

^{*}Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, and INESC TEC (Porto, Portugal)

[†]NVISION (Spain)

[‡]Centro de Electrónica Industrial, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)

Abstract—The rapid proliferation of Edge AI applications demands efficient, low-power computing architectures tailored to specific workloads. The RISC-V ecosystem is a promising solution, and has led to a fast growth of implementations based on custom instructions extensions, but with varying degrees of functionality and support which may hinder easy adoption.

In this paper, we extensively review existing RISC-V extensions targeting primarily the AI domain and respective compilation flows, highlighting challenges in deployment, usability, and compatibility. We further implement and provide usable containerized environments for two of these works. To address the identified challenges, we then propose an approach for lightweight early validation of custom instructions via source-to-source transformations, without need of compiler modifications. We target our own Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) accelerator, which we integrate into a CORE-V cv32e40px baseline core through custom instructions, and versus which we achieve up to $11.9\times$ speedup for matrix-vector operations.

Index Terms—RISC-V, Source-to-source, Edge AI, Custom extensions

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for ever more efficient computation is driven by the growing demand for higher performance under constrained power budgets. Stringent low-power requirements must be met to enable edge computing at scale, for which the growth of edge Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a motive force. The RISC-V ecosystem, due to its open nature and focus on customization, has led to the emergence of a considerable number of state-of-the-art works to address this through customized RISC-V cores, including full System-on-Chips (SoCs) designs. Despite this, the ease of use of these systems is compromised. This is due on one hand to the difficulty in reproducing the required development environment and toolchain dependencies, and on the other hand by the lack of compilation support to properly exploit the acceleration potential more ubiquitously. Thus, use of the designs and exploitation of their micro-architectural advancements is commonly limited to either identified or coded use-cases.

In this paper, we present our own hardware design and supporting custom instructions for a RISC-V core that targets matrix multiplication kernels of several bit-widths, which are

widely used in Neural Network (NN) models. We present experimental speedup results versus a baseline RISC-V core, but also address the state-of-the-art limitations on compilation by proposing a flow which is meant to act as a lightweight early support of custom extensions that does not require compiler or assemble modification. To put this contribution into perspective, we first conducted an extended literature review to identify common issues regarding usability and compilation support of state-of-the-art work. We also evaluate the required effort to deploy and use a subset of these works, and contribute to improving their usability by creating and freely providing Docker containers for them.

Thus, our contributions are:

- An extended literature review which, to the best of our knowledge, is the first to analyze limitations on the usability of RISC-V extensions for AI;
- An implementation of a configurable matrix multiplication unit, which is integrated into the state-of-the-art eXtensible Heterogenous Energy-Efficient Platform (X-HEEP) platform [1];
- A performance evaluation of our unit versus a scalar baseline, and also versus SIMD capable RISC-V cores;
- A flow for insertion of the custom instructions based on source-to-source analysis of high-level code.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents our literature review focusing on existing RISC-V customization works targeting primarily AI workloads; in Section III, we detail the required effort to bring up and use a restricted selection of the reviewed works and contribute to improving their usability by creating and freely providing Docker containers for them; in Section IV we present the hardware details for our hardware accelerator as well as the compilation flow for insertion of instructions; in Section V we present hardware synthesis results and execution times of our accelerator versus scalar and SIMD baselines; finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

We review state-of-the-art works that aim to customize RISC-V cores with AI oriented extensions, covering architectural details and compiler support. To the best of our knowledge, few similar reviews exist, especially including a usability study of the available works. We summarize our analysis in Table I.

This work has been financially supported by the A-IQ READY project, which has received funding within the Chips Joint Undertaking (Chips JU) – the Public-Private Partnership for research, development, and innovation under Horizon Europe – and National Authorities under grant agreement No. 101096658

Overall, there are several works in the literature that address RISC-V extensions for edge AI use cases. Many of these extensions focus on SIMD operations and instructions for smaller bit-widths, both for integer and floating representations. While most designs provide significant speedups and energy efficiency improvements, they often lack compiler support. In most cases, using the custom extensions requires manual intervention (e.g., inline assembly), or no details on how to use the instructions are provided. The `cv32e40p` is the only core in this study with open-source compiler support, an even then there are still limitations in the automatic optimization of certain custom instructions, such as dot-products and post-increment load/store operations.

The following sections detail each of these works, among which we targeted *CORE-V + X-HEEP* and *RNNASIP* for testing and containerization, resulting in freely available Docker files that address usability issues.

A. CV32E40P

The `cv32e40p` [2] is a RISC-V core supporting the RV32IMC instruction set, with configurable support for either the F or Zfinx standard Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs), as well as the CORE-V custom ISA extensions group, containing various ISA extensions developed by PULP which have been shown to accelerate AI workloads. The extensions include instructions for hardware loops, load and store operations with pointer post-increment, various bit manipulation operations, integer Multiply-And-Accumulate (MAC) operations and SIMD operations, which are common operations in AI kernels. A modified GCC allows for compiler-level support for a subset of the introduced instructions. However, a set of built-ins is also available for the majority of the extensions, eliminating at least the need for manual inline assembly.

The authors show that for typical Digital Signal Processing (DSP) workloads the proposed core is on average $3.5\times$ faster and $3.2\times$ more energy efficient. Overall, the proposed `cv32e40p`, as well as PULP – the platform it originated from – are some of the most advanced open-source RISC-V non-standard ISA extensions presently available, and their toolchain support is also mostly unmatched. Despite this, some current compiler-level shortcomings include limited automatic opportunity detection and insertion of some instructions. For example, compiler generated post-increment load and store operations are limited to single-nested loops, and instructions that implement dot-products can only be used explicitly in source-code through built-ins.

B. RNNASIP

Andri et al. [3] aim to accelerate Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) inference for Radio Resource Management (RRM) applications. In this field, devices typically stay on the field for long periods of time, yet the algorithms evolve at a fast pace. As such, devices must be efficient but adaptable, and the authors consider Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) to be too costly for dense and widespread deployment. Instead, three instructions were added to RISCY [9], a predecessor

core to the `cv32e40p` developed as part of the PULP platform, with existing support for various ISA extensions. An algorithm was implemented using only the standard IMFC instructions, and re-implemented with resort to the PULP’s extensions. By comparing performance results, performance critical operations were identified that informed the design of the three custom instructions. Namely, instructions that each compute a sigmoid, a hyperbolic tangent, and a combination of a sum-dot-product operation.

When combining the existing PULP extensions with these three custom instructions and software optimizations, the core is on average $15\times$ faster versus code using only the base RISC-V IMFC ISA, and the overall energy efficiency shows a $10\times$ improvement. The baseline implementation is compiled using the standard GCC 7.1.1 for RISC-V RV32IMFC ISA, but any required modifications to support the added instructions are not explicitly explained. However, the code repository hosting the work contains C test files for the custom instructions where these are introduced using inline assembly. Thus, to the best of our understanding, the compiler does not automatically optimize programs to use these instructions.

C. Minifloat-NN

Bertaccini et al. [4] extend and open-source Floating Point Unit (FPU) called FPnew [10], in order to support an existing extension called *smallFloat* [11]. They then implement, to the best of our understanding, three new custom instructions extending *smallFloat* itself. These are an Expanding Sum-of-dot-product (ExSdotp) operation, as well as expanding and non-expanding three-operand additions named Vector Inner Sum (Vsum) and Expanding Vector Inner Sum (ExVsum), where an “expanding” operation produces an output with wider bit-width than its inputs. Specifically, ExSdotp computes the dot product of `rs1` and `rs2`, and performs a three component sum with the results and the value of `rd`. Vsum computes a three component sum `rs1`, `rs2`, and `rd`. ExVsum computes a three component sum between the packed values in `rs1` with the value in `rd`. The `rd` register functions as an accumulator for all instructions, and for ExSdotp and ExVsum it contains data packed in higher precision than `rs1` and `rs2`. Different instruction suffixes encode input and outputs precision as either 8 bit, 16 bit, or 32 bit.

The FPU accepts 64 bit inputs and 64 bit outputs, and through parametrization during instantiation it can be used to compute SIMD operations over different bit widths. Specifically, the unit can perform up to two 16 bit to 32 bit operations per cycle, or four 8 bit to 16 bit operations per cycle, by packing the inputs and outputs into the full width 64 bit ports. The FPU supports all conventional floating-point operations for every enabled floating-point format, except the square root and division operations.

The proposed FPU achieves the highest energy efficiency when executing low-precision kernels when compared to two state-of-the-art architectures [12], [13] that also support low-precision operations as well as the unmodified FPnew unit, being $1.7\times$ more efficient than one, and $14.4\times$ then the second.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF STATE-OF-THE-ART APPROACHES BASED ON RISC-V CUSTOMIZATION

Work	Open Source	Extensions	Compiler Support	Our Docker
CV32E40P [2]	Yes ¹ ✓	Hardware loops, post-incr. ld/st, SIMD, dot-product, bit manipulation	Modified GCC ✓	Yes ² ✓
RNNASIP [3]	Yes ³ ✓	Sigmoid, tanh, sum-dot-product insts.	No (inline assembly) ✗	Yes ² ✓
Minifloat-NN [4]	Yes ⁴ ✓	ExSdotp, Vsum, ExVsum (for FP8, FP16, FP32)	No ✗	No ✗
Kumar <i>et al.</i> [5]	No ✗	64-bit load/store insts.	Codasip (proprietary) ✓	No ✗
Bernardo <i>et al.</i> [6]	No ✗	3 (unspecified) + zero-overhead loops	Partial (unclear description)	No ✗
RISCV-FNT [7]	No ✗	FNT for CNNs (SIMD, compute-in-memory)	No (inline assembly) ✗	No ✗
RV-GEMM [8]	No ✗	Matrix Multiplication (GEMM, SIMD)	No ✗	No ✗

¹<https://github.com/pulp-platform/pulp-nn-mixed>, ²<https://github.com/specs-feup/riscv-ai-extensions>, ³<https://github.com/andrire/RNNASIP>,

⁴<https://github.com/openhwgroup/cvfpv>

It is also $1.3\times$ more efficient than the original FPnew for the lowest precision operations, and doubles its performance when using the expanding operations. We have also not identified any other work supporting 8 bit floating-point operations.

However, no details are given on code generation or compiler support to exploit the instructions. Furthermore, performance for higher-precision kernels is not evaluated, and although the FPU is compared to two existing works, the comparison is skewed as data of different precisions is employed for each case. Finally, one of the reference works for comparison outperforms the proposed FPU in terms of throughput by $1.42\times$.

D. Supporting 64-bit Operands in 32-bit RISC-V Cores

Kumar *et al.* [5] extended the RISC-V 32 bit ISA with two custom instructions to load and store 64 bit operands. This is implemented by grouping the 32 32 bit general purpose registers into 16 pairs of 64 bit registers, which are then used as operands for the custom instructions. There is also an on-going effort by the RISC-V consortium to standardize such an approach¹. The ISA extension is implemented on Codasip [14], a framework for designing RISC-V Intellectual Properties (IPs), which also generates a supporting Standard Developer Kit (SDK). Although this simplifies the inclusion of compiler hints for the custom instructions, the approach is not yet able to optimize generic C code, and explicit consecutive memory accesses must be written at the source code level.

The extension was tested on a single C program compiled and profiled with the proprietary Codasip compiler. The code declares a two dimensional data array, and copies its elements to a distinct target array. The implemented 64 bit memory instructions resulted in a 50 % reduction in the number of clock cycles and a 30 % reduction of power consumption during memory and load instruction with only a 4 % area increase. Future work will address support for generic user C code and the `bfloat16` datatype.

¹<https://github.com/riscv/riscv-zilsd>

E. Platform for Intelligent Sensor Processing

Bernardo *et al.* [6] discuss the implementation of a RISC-V core targeting audio event detection (Intelligent Sensor Processing) acceleration for edge applications. The design features a core built upon Minres TGC and an UltraTrail AI hardware accelerator, while the underlying SoC is an adapted version of Pulpissimo [15]. The core features three unspecified custom instructions as well as a zero overhead loop feature encoded using CoreDSL, a language for ISA specification. The Ultra-Trail accelerator provides an TVM UMA (Universal Modular Accelerator Interface) API, which allows an easy integration of new hardware accelerators into TVM. All instructions were manually implemented as Register Transfer Level (RTL) and then integrated into the core using SCAIE-V, an open-source hardware interface custom extensions, while the Instruction Set Simulator (ISS) was based on CoreDSL. However, it is not open-sourced. Toolchain aspects on compiler support for the custom instructions are not detailed. When running an audio event detection application the core was able to achieve a $2.15\times$ speedup and a 27 % power reduction compared to a base implementation without the ISA extension.

F. RISCV-FNT

RISCV-FNT [7] is a RISC-V based on RISCY [9] that aims to accelerate Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) via the Fermat Number Theorem (FNT), which replaces complex numbers with real numbers in Fast Fourier Transforms (FFTs). The core, which includes an FNT acceleration unit, is written in Verilog and was implemented on an FPGA. The acceleration unit is controlled using custom instructions, features SIMD and compute-in-memory capabilities. It can process an 8×8 matrix at once or larger matrices in a sliding window fashion. There is no mention of software or toolchain support, and instead, inline assembly is used to control the unit. A speedup of $8.5\times$ is achieved versus baseline RISC-V processors without FNT – presumably the RISCY core – though this speedup is specific to the `conv2d` layer. For 1D Convolution (`conv1d`) the speedup is $6.2\times$, and the overall speedup for the neural network is $3.6\times$, together with a 40 % power consumption reduction.

G. RV-GEMM

RV-GEMM [8] is a RISC-V [9] based core featuring a coprocessor to accelerate general matrix multiplication, a common operation in AI kernels. The coprocessor implements SIMD operations and is controlled by the core via three custom instructions. It features 16 parallel multiplication units with configurable precision integer operands (32 bit, 16 bit or 8 bit), as well as 8 input data registers, 8 control registers and 16 output data registers for a total of 32 32 bit registers. The custom instructions set the dimensions of the input matrices and operand precision, trigger the calculation of up to 4×4 blocks of the output matrix, and copy these blocks to a target address. The modified core achieved speedups of $15.8\times$, $28.7\times$, and $42.5\times$ for General Matrix Multiplication (GEMM) computations under 32 bit, 16 bit and 8 bit operand precision respectively when compared to the unmodified RISC-V core, while only increasing the overall power consumption by 2.6%. However, although control and address generation units are mentioned, no detailed explanation is given on how the custom instructions need to be orchestrated to access matrix data which is non-contiguous in memory. Example code is not shown nor is the supporting toolchain mentioned or open-sourced.

III. DOCKER CONTAINERS FOR STATE-OF-THE-ART PLATFORMS

We address two works from our review, for which we accessed the public artifacts, attempted to replicate their example use-cases or provided tutorial flows, identified usability issues, and resolved dependencies. We produced Docker files for these two cases, to promote fast usability of the platforms².

A. CORE-V + X-HEEP

The X-HEEP [1] is an open-source configurable SoC based on RISC-V, designed to support the integration of custom low-power accelerators. The SoC can use three core types from the CORE-V family by the OpenHW Group [16], including the `cv32e40p`. Co-processors can be attached through the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF), which allows for custom instructions to be dispatched to an external module with operands and results being exchanged via the register file, without need to modify the core itself. The eXtensible Accelerator InterFace (XAIF) provides native support for a wide range of memory-mapped accelerators with different area, power, and performance constraints, enabling the reuse of IPs. The SoC can be tested through RTL simulators or SystemC models, and can be deployed on FPGAs.

Through SystemVerilog templates, the supported customizations include the core type and enabled features, the bus topology (one-at-a-time or fully connected), memory addressing mode, memory bank number and size, and peripherals including a platform-level interrupt controller, a timer, General Purpose Input/Output, I2C and Serial Peripheral Interface.

²<https://github.com/specs-feup/riscv-ai-extensions>

1) *Testing and Containerizing*: The X-HEEP platform supports several cores and simulators. Despite existing documentation, the indicated toolchain is not able to compile the PULP custom instructions supported by the `cv32e40p`, one of the supported cores. For our testing and containerization process, we selected `cv32e40pv2`, the second iteration of `cv32e40p`, as the core to instantiate. This core is under active development, so existing issues are propagated to the usability of X-HEEP. Regardless, it is not clear from the X-HEEP documentation which compilation toolchain and respective version is required to target this specific core. In [9], use of the PULP toolchain is referred, and the PULP documentation then indicates Embecosm's CORE-V toolchain³. Even so, we had to resolve additional outdated Python dependencies by editing configuration files of X-HEEP's build flow, as well as minor edits to Verilator's source code.

After these steps, we created a test suite for the core's supported custom instructions, largely adapted from OpenHW Group's existing test suite⁴. The tests had to be modified in order to be compilable and runnable in the X-HEEP environment. The specific issue was a re-encoding of the instructions of `cv32e40pv2` versus `cv32e40p`, including a standardization of the instruction's prefix to "`cv`". This meant that the assembly calls of instructions were no longer compilable and had to be rewritten manually. In fact, test written in pure assembly files were entirely unsupported, therefore we re-implemented them as inline assembly embedded in C functions. Furthermore, tests targeting the post-increment load and store instructions used hard-coded and, as we understood, arbitrary values for the memory addresses, which exceeded the simulated memory range, leading the simulation process to fail. Finally, we also created new tests for hardware loops, and created support scripts for testing. These handle the multiple steps involved in compiling a test and executing it, and address scenarios where the tests fail to terminate due to bugs, otherwise leading to lockups.

B. RNNASIP

The RNNASIP system [3], which we have previously presented. The system is based on an extended RISC-V [9], targeting recurrent neural networks with three custom instructions, supported by a fork of the PULP RISC-V toolchain.

1) *Testing and Containerizing*: The RNNASIP design was last updated in 2019, which compromises its usability for new tool versions and operating systems. According to the documentation, we employed a CentOS 7.9 machine to reproduce installation and execution of provided tests, in order to understand the requirements to produce a respective container. Since CentOS 7.9 reached end-of-life in early 2024, this entailed configuring the package manager to resort to vaulted repositories. Furthermore, the versions of RNNASIP's dependencies are mismatched with the operating system's defaults, which required installing additional versions of Python2 and

³<https://embecosm.com/downloads/tool-chain-downloads>

⁴<https://github.com/openhwgroup/core-v-verif>

Fig. 1. Multiplator pipeline stages. Inter-stage registers are optionally enabled.

Python3, the respective packages (with explicit permission for installation of deprecated packages), and finally modifying the hashbang of RNNASIP’s own shell scripts to point to the correct Python executables. Next, we had to ensure the dependencies were installed and reconcile the operating system’s defaults with the project’s expected versions. After installing both Python2 and Python3 and their respective PIP versions, we installed the python dependencies while explicitly allowing deprecated packages, and force others to use the correct python version by modifying the shebang in their bin/ scripts. We also set `cmake3` as the default `cmake` version through a symbolic link. Finally, the process of identified and installing dependencies also required changing a `git` repository URL in RNNASIP’s configuration file to SSH, since HTTP support has been deprecated. All of these aspects significantly underscore the difficulty in using state-of-the-art designs without proper support, hindering the exploitation of promising research results for future work.

IV. SIMD MULTIPLY-ACCUMULATOR FOR VARIABLE PRECISION LOW-POWER AI

To address common operations found in NN models, we implement and evaluate an accelerator unit for matrix operations, suitable for operations like matrix multiplication, which supports variable precision operands, SIMD execution, sub-word dot product and MAC operations. The following sections explain the hardware architecture, how we integrated the unit with a RISC-V core as custom instructions, and the high-level compilation flow to identify instruction insertion opportunities.

A. Multiplator Accelerator Unit Design

Operations between matrices are abundant in NN models. To achieve a viable deployment on embedded platforms, under low power and resource constraints, quantization is a common technique [17]. The number of bits for the parameters of the quantized model depends on the desired accuracy and size of the model, on a per-model basis. We have implemented a configurable SIMD multiplier-accumulator unit, *Multiplator*, capable of variable-precision operations, thus targeting a range of possible quantizations for vector-vector, matrix-vector and matrix-matrix operations. According to the runtime width of the operands, the unit enables SIMD operations by reusing hardware, exploiting parallelism and accelerating inference.

The unit supports one 32 bit multiplication in scalar mode, and depending on the configuration, two 16 bit, four 8 bit, eight 4 bit, and up to sixteen 2 bit multiplications. As data is packed in 32 bit words, there are no multiple data transfers

Fig. 2. CV-X-IF based control logic providing a custom instruction interface to a *Multiplator* instance.

when sub-word datatype is used. *Multiplator* tackles the mixed precision problem when targeting NN acceleration. Most NN accelerators are designed and optimized for a specific data type and are not configurable at runtime [18], hindering support for mixed precision operations within the same model or support for differently quantized models.

Figure 1 illustrates a high-level view of the unit’s pipeline, which is composed of three stages exploiting known hardware design techniques. Namely, the unit is based on a Booth encoder, a Wallace tree for product reduction, and finally a Carry Look-Ahead Adder (CLA) for final summation. The Booth encoder allows for reduction of the number of partial products in multiplication, by transforming the multiplication operation into additions, subtractions, or shifts. The Wallace tree reduces all partial products into two final operands at logarithmic complexity, whilst also reducing the critical path of the circuit since reduction occurs in parallel. It also enables the dot product operation via internal multiplexer re-routing. The two final 32 bit operands are added in the CLA. In our design, the inter-stage registers are optionally instantiated, and we evaluate the resulting difference in operating frequency in Section V.

B. Custom Instruction integration through CV-X-IF

We have integrated a single *Multiplator* unit into the state-of-the-art SoC X-HEEP. This platform allows for selection of four RISC-V cores to act as the main processor, among which we chose the `cv32e40px` core. This core is equipped with the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF), enabling implementation of instruction extensions in a coprocessor without the need to modify the core itself [19]. We have designed control and instruction decode logic, shown in Figure 2, to enable the use of the one instance of *Multiplator* via a set of custom instructions. This wrapper module has been designed in a generic manner to manage the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF) interface, and can be leveraged for future additional extensions. The core will attempt to offload any instruction

```

// .insn r opcode6, func3, func7, rd, rs1, rs2
static inline void mac_8b_custom (signed int a,
signed int b, signed int c, signed int d) {
asm volatile (
".insn r 0b0001011, 0x02, 0x0, x0, %[RS1], %[RS2]\n"
// 8b config - MAC - custom0 (Instruction 1)
".insn r 0b0001011, 0x02, 0x0, x0, %[RS3], %[RS4]"
// 8b config - MAC - custom0 (Instruction 2)
:
: [RS1] "r"(a), [RS2] "r"(b), [RS3] "r"(c), [RS4] "r"(d)
);
}

```

Fig. 3. Macro encoding the pair custom instructions which configure the accelerator for a 4-bit configuration. Configurations for 8 bit, 16 bit, or 32 bit are analogous, by specifying different arguments for *RS1* and *RS2*.

that it does not recognize from its base instruction set to the interface. From CV-X-IF specification, we employ the *Issue Interface* which signals which instructions need to be offloaded, including their register-based operands, the *Commit Interface* to indicate accepted or discarded instructions, and the *Result Interface* to signal execution status and feed data back to the core’s register file.

C. Custom Instruction Insertion via Source-to-Source

As seen in Section II, there are two main approaches regarding the use of custom instructions: manual insertion of instructions in the source code and modification of an existing established compiler (e.g. GCC). The first approach requires less upfront costs for the provider of the custom instructions, but may represent a significant entry barrier for the software developer, and is error-prone. The second approach requires considerable upfront cost for the provider, but is transparent to the software developer. We propose a middle-term approach, where the custom instructions are automatically inserted directly in the source code using a source-to-source compiler. This is similar to the approach of modifying an existing compiler but with what we consider a lower upfront cost. It also avoids compiler lock-in and can support new compiler versions. This approach has been previously demonstrated for custom extensions in other domains [20].

To support this for the *Multiplicator*, we first define a set of C macros that invoke the custom instructions, as exemplified in Figure 3. In the example we include two custom instructions per macro call to avoid common cycle penalty known in the cv32e40px core. We resort to an inline assembly feature natively supported by the RISC-V assembler, which allows for custom instructions to be invoked without the need for custom mnemonics. Instead, the values of each field of a particular instruction format are directly specified, which in our case are always R-type instructions. In other words, and unlike other architectures, forking the assembler to support custom mnemonics for the new instructions can be circumvented.

The execution results shown in Section V are relative to benchmarks where these macros were manually inserted for straightforward cases. Aiming to improve this, Figure 4 shows our under-development flow to insert these macros automatically. We employ a source-to-source compiler, Clava, capable of parsing C/C++ code, performing analysis and transformation passes of the Abstract Syntax Tree (AST), and

Fig. 4. Flowchart diagram of the proposed compilation and testing process of lightweight custom instruction source-to-source passes.

emitting transformed code [21]. Passes are specified externally through TypeScript files, meaning the compiler engine itself does not need to be modified for any particular use-case.

By specifying analysis passes to identify acceleration opportunities, we can then modify the code (e.g., edit or remove loops and statement) to replace code segments with functionally equivalent macro calls to *Multiplicator*. The resulting modified C/C++ file can be compiled conventionally (i.e., with a RISC-V gcc build). During our development of these passes, we can easily compare the computed results with those produced by the original unmodified code. Further, we can compare the automatically inserted macros to our existing manually written modified kernels, to validate that the compiler captures the same, or more, acceleration opportunities.

Based on this flow, Figure 5a shows an example of the code we wish to target, and Figure 5b shows a proposal of an applied transformation that inserts the MAC operations after identifying an opportunity for use. There are source-to-source approaches that already allow complex source code analysis and manipulation [21], [22], including the construction of Control-Flow Graphs (CFGs) and normalization of code, which will be the basis for this work. On top of that existing work, we will add analysis and transformations that are specific to *Multiplicator*’s capabilities.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We compare our core with the state-of-the-art CORE-V PULP instructions [19], which are implemented in the cv32e40p and cv32e40px core included in X-HEEP. Notable instructions in this extension include hardware loops, post-increment loads and stores, and SIMD sub-word dot product instructions. Our primary goal was to compare our solution with the SIMD dot product instruction. We employ a baremetal code kernel executing a matrix-vector multiplication where the matrix size is (64, 784) and the input vector is (784, 1). Additionally, we present hardware synthesis results regarding operating frequency and resource requirements, for different configurations of the *Multiplicator* pipeline.

A. Experimental Results: Hardware Synthesis

We have synthesized the *Multiplicator* core instantiated in the CV-X-IF wrapper logic with full register pipeline, targeting a

```

int8_t iv[IV_MAX_LEN];
int8_t im[MAT_MAX_LEN];
int32_t outvec[OV_MAX_LEN];
uint16_t ivlen;
uint16_t ovlen;
// ... initializations

// Compute using SW
for (int i=0; i < ovlen; i++) {
    int32_t acc = 0;

    for (int j=0; j < ivlen; j++)
        acc += im[j+i*ivlen] * iv[j];
    outvec[i] = acc;
}

// ...previous declarations and initializations
// process 32 bits at a time instead of 8 bits
const uint16_t ivfactor = sizeof(uint32_t)/sizeof(int8_t);
const uint16_t ivnewlen = ivlen / ivfactor;
const uint32_t* im32bit = reinterpret_cast<uint32_t*>(im);

// Compute using HW (Two MAC operations per iteration)
for (int i = 0; i < ov_len; i++) {
    const uint32_t* iv32bit = reinterpret_cast<uint32_t*>(iv);

    for (uint16_t j = 0; j < ivnewlen; j += 2)
        mac_8b_custom(i_32bit[j+i*ivnewlen], im32bit[j],
            iv32bit[j+i*ivnewlen+1], im32bit[j+1]);
    outvec[i] = read_clear_custom(); // Read and clear acc
}

```

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Example of a) Software version of a matrix-vector multiplication, and b) transformed version using source-to-source compilation of the matrix-vector multiplication that uses custom instructions.

TABLE II
RESOURCE REQUIREMENTS OF *Multiplator*

Hierarchy	LUTs	FFs
Top Level	3393	1566
Execution Block	2939	757
Multiplator Config.	2877	649
Multiplator Unit	2812	579
Booth	1966	0
Wallace	814	0
CLA	30	0
Accumulator	60	32
Interface	442	809

a ZUBoard-1CG device which contains an AMD UltraScale+ MPSoC XCZU1CG, the smallest device in this family.

Table II shows the resource requirements of the unit for a synthesis run with preserved hierarchy. We employed AMD Vivado 2024.1 for synthesis, with options `-mode = out-of-context` and `-flatten_hierarchy = none`. The *Multiplator* unit alone represents 83% of the Lookup Tables (LUTs) and 37% of the Flip Flops (FFs) of the entire module. The remaining resources are related to the instruction decoding and interface logic. The depth of the control FIFOs can be optimized to save additional registers, the depth used in the experiment was 4, which would allow a maximum of 4 instructions offloaded in the co-processor. When not preserving the hierarchy, the synthesis process is more efficient, and the total number of LUTs and FFs required for the design are 3393 and 1566 respectively.

Table IIIa) shows the maximum operating frequency and worst negative slack for the individual stages of the unit. For an intentionally high target clock frequency of 1 GHz, which was set to push the synthesis tool for best-effort, the stages achieve around half of this target. However, all maximum operating frequencies are similar, indicating that no stage is a particular bottleneck and that the pipeline is balanced.

Table IIIb) shows analogous results for different configurations of inter-stage registers. A fully combinatorial unit (first row) achieves an operating frequency of 157 MHz, and a fully registered stage maintains a higher frequency of 400 MHz in the best case. This shows that our design can be

TABLE III
MAXIMUM OPERATING FREQUENCY FOR MULTIPLATOR STAGES

(a) results for individual stages

Stage	Tclk	WNS	Delay	Max Freq.
Booth	1 ns	-0.929 ns	1.929 ns	518.40 MHz
Wallace	1 ns	-0.910 ns	1.910 ns	523.56 MHz
CLA	1 ns	-1.064 ns	2.064 ns	484.50 MHz

(b) results for different inter-stage register configurations

Stage Configs.	Tclk	WNS	Delay	Max Freq.
1 (B + W + C)	2 ns	-4.345 ns	6.345 ns	157.60 MHz
2 (B / W + C)	2 ns	-2.306 ns	4.306 ns	232.23 MHz
2 (B + W / C)	2 ns	-1.696 ns	3.696 ns	270.56 MHz
3 (B / W / C)	2 ns	-0.554 ns	2.554 ns	391.54 MHz
3 (B / W / C)	1 ns	-1.498 ns	2.498 ns	400.32 MHz

B = Booth, W = Wallace, C = CLA, "+" = combinatorial, "/" = registered

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE OF *Multiplator* VS. SCALAR CPU AND SIMD PULP INSTRUCTIONS

	Cycles	MAC8 p/cycle	MACs p/iteration	Speedup
cv32e40px	452104	0.111	1	1.0×
cv32e40px ¹	232710	0.216	8	1.94×
CORE-V SIMD-DOT ²	69571	0.721	4	7.2×
CORE-V SIMD-DOT ³	42503	1.181	32	11.8×
<i>Multiplator</i> ²	69898	0.718	4	7.2×
<i>Multiplator</i> ³	42122	1.191	32	11.9×

¹(8x unrolling), ²(inner loop with 2 SIMD insts. – equivalent to 2x unrolling),

³(8x unrolling of inner loop with 2 SIMD insts.) – equivalent to 16x unrolling)

instantiated in architectures with fairly high timing constraints. Considering both cycle count and clock period, the fully combinatorial design minimizes unit latency but compromises overall performance due to its critical path. The two-register configuration (B + W / C) achieves the second lowest total latency (only 16% longer than the fully combinatorial case) whilst maintaining a higher operating frequency, making it a balanced configuration choice.

B. Experimental Results: Execution Times

We resort to cycle-accurate simulation based on Verilator to run our matrix-vector multiplication test kernel. We conduct this simulation for several targets, shown Table I, where the baseline is the `cv32e40px`. To compile code for the cases of the baseline, and for those with our *Multiplator* macros, we use the official RISC-V `gcc` compiler with `-O2` optimization flag. To generate binaries containing the CORE-V instructions, we used the modified compiler by the OpenHW Group [23].

We executed the kernel employing a data-width of 8 bit per datum, which is the smallest SIMD granularity supported by CORE-V. Thus we get a fair comparison between the platforms, although *Multiplator* can compute at 2 bit precision, where the performance gains would scale linearly based on these 8 bit results. We evaluated unrolled versions of the code, and others without unrolling. The baseline executes scalar code, which we also evaluate with $8x$ unrolling. Since CORE-V and *Multiplator* execute two SIMD instructions per iteration, this is equivalent to an implicit $2x$ unrolling, which when explicitly unrolled in code by $8x$ provides an equivalent unrolling of $16x$. We achieve comparable performance with the CORE-V SIMD dot-product instructions, outperforming the baseline. Namely, we compute 1.19 MACs/cycle on the *Multiplator*, which is a $11.9\times$ speed-up over the 0.099 MACs/cycle for the baseline and a slight improvement over the CORE-V SIMD implementation.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we reviewed state-of-the-art RISC-V extensions for AI and highlighted challenges in compilation and usability. We provide two container environments to address immediate usability issues, but further we address overall compilation support through a source-to-source approach for insertion of custom instructions. We presented our *Multiplator* accelerator for SIMD matrix-vector operations, integrated into a `cv32e40` through custom instructions and the Core-V eXtension interface (CV-X-IF), where we demonstrate comparable performance to a state-of-the-art approach. By implementing SIMD operations externally via CV-X-IF, simple cores compliant with the interface, and without the full set of CORE-V extensions, can leverage the accelerator for specific SIMD needs, resulting a compact alternative relative to the larger extension set in cores like the baseline `cv32e40`.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Machetti, P. D. Schiavone, T. C. Müller, M. Peón-Quirós, and D. Aienza, "X-heep: An open-source, configurable and extendible RISC-V microcontroller for the exploration of ultra-low-power edge accelerators," *arXiv preprint*, vol. arXiv:2401.05548, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.05548>
- [2] OpenHW Group, "CV32E40P 32-bit RISC-V Processor Core," <https://github.com/openhwgroup/cv32e40p>, 2024, Accessed: 2024-12-17.
- [3] R. Andri, T. Henriksson, and L. Benini, "Extending the risc-v isa for efficient rnn-based 5g radio resource management," in *2020 57th ACM/IEEE Design Automation Conference (DAC)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [4] L. Bertaccini, G. Paulin, T. Fischer, S. Mach, and L. Benini, "Minifloat-nn and xsdotp: An isa extension and a modular open hardware unit for low-precision training on risc-v cores," in *2022 IEEE 29th Symposium on Computer Arithmetic (ARITH)*, 2022, pp. 1–8.

- [5] A. Kumar M, V. Kumar, D. John, and S. Shanker, "Implementation and analysis of custom instructions on risc-v for edge-ai applications," in *Proceedings of the 14th International Symposium on Highly Efficient Accelerators and Reconfigurable Technologies*, ser. HEART '24. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2024, p. 126–129. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3665283.3665342>
- [6] P. P. Bernardo, P. Schmid, O. Bringmann, M. Iftekhar, B. Sadiye, W. Mueller, A. Koch, E. Jentzsch, A. Sauer, I. Feldner, and W. Ecker, "A scalable RISC-v hardware platform for intelligent sensor processing," in *2024 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)*, 2024, pp. 1–5.
- [7] B. Chen, X. Wang, Y. Huang, and Z. Xu, "RISCV-FNT: A fast FNT-based RISC-v processor for CNN acceleration," in *Proceedings of the 6th ACM International Conference on AI Circuits and Systems (AICAS) 2024*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 292–296.
- [8] X. Wang, C. Feng, B. Chen, Q. Wang, Y. Huang, and T. T. Ye, "Rv-gemm: Neural network inference acceleration with near-memory gemm instructions on risc-v," in *Proceedings of the 21st ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers*, ser. CF '24. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2024, p. 302–305. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649153.3649181>
- [9] M. Gautschi, P. D. Schiavone, A. Traber, I. Loi, A. Pullini, D. Rossi, E. Flamand, F. K. Gürkaynak, and L. Benini, "Near-threshold risc-v core with dsp extensions for scalable iot endpoint devices," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 25, no. 10, pp. 2700–2713, 2017.
- [10] S. Mach, F. Schuiki, F. Zaruba, and L. Benini, "Fpnew: An open-source multiformat floating-point unit architecture for energy-proportional transprecision computing," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 774–787, 2021.
- [11] G. Tagliavini, S. Mach, D. Rossi, A. Marongiu, and L. Benini, "Design and evaluation of smallfloat simd extensions to the risc-v isa," in *2019 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE)*, 2019, pp. 654–657.
- [12] W. Mao, K. Li, Q. Cheng, L. Dai, B. Li, X. Xie, H. Li, L. Lin, and H. Yu, "A configurable floating-point multiple-precision processing element for hpc and ai converged computing," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 213–226, 2022.
- [13] H. Zhang, D. Chen, and S.-B. Ko, "Efficient multiple-precision floating-point fused multiply-add with mixed-precision support," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 68, no. 7, pp. 1035–1048, 2019.
- [14] CudasipTM, "Cudasip," <https://cudasip.com/>, 2023, website Accessed: 2024-12-17.
- [15] P. D. Schiavone, D. Rossi, A. Pullini, A. Di Mauro, F. Conti, and L. Benini, "Quentin: an Ultra-Low-Power PULPissimo SoC in 22nm FDX," in *IEEE SOI-3D-Subthreshold Microelectronics Technology Unified Conference (S3S)*, 2018, pp. 1–3.
- [16] OpenHW Group, "Open-source processors and platforms," <https://www.openhwgroup.org/>, 2024, website Accessed: 2024-12-17.
- [17] O. Weng, "Neural network quantization for efficient inference: A survey," *CoRR*, vol. abs/2112.06126, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.06126>
- [18] C. Silvano, D. Ielmini, F. Ferrandi, L. Fiorin, S. Curzel, L. Benini, F. Conti, A. Garofalo, C. Zambelli, E. Calore, S. F. Schifano, M. Palesi, G. Ascia, D. Patti, N. Petra, D. D. Caro, L. Lavagno, T. Urso, V. Cardellini, G. C. Cardarilli, R. Birke, and S. Perri, "A survey on deep learning hardware accelerators for heterogeneous hpc platforms," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.15552>
- [19] OpenHW Group, "Cv32e40p instruction set extensions documentation," https://cv32e40p.readthedocs.io/en/latest/instruction_set_extensions.html, 2025, accessed: 2025-02-11.
- [20] M. Henriques, J. Bispo, and N. Paulino, "Using source-to-source to target risc-v custom extensions: Uve case-study," in *Proceedings of the 16th Workshop on Rapid Simulation and Performance Evaluation for Design*, 2024, pp. 42–50.
- [21] J. Bispo and J. M. Cardoso, "Clava: C/c++ source-to-source compilation using lara," *SoftwareX*, vol. 12, p. 100565, 2020.
- [22] D. Quinlan and C. Liao, "The rose source-to-source compiler infrastructure," in *Cetus users and compiler infrastructure workshop, in conjunction with PACT*, vol. 2011. Citeseer, 2011, p. 1.
- [23] Embecosm Buildbot, "Core-v compiler," <https://buildbot.embecosm.com/job/corev-gcc-ubuntu2004/50/artifact/corev-openhw-gcc-ubuntu2004-20240530.tar.gz>, 2024, version for Ubuntu 20.04 (amd64), accessed on 30 May 2024.